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Green Leadership and Sustainable Consumption Behavior: A Dual-Path Mediation via Pro-Environmental Behavior and Green Literacy

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ABSTRACT

Environmental degradation is widely recognized as a serious global challenge that is intensifying at an alarming pace in the current era. Its continuous acceleration poses significant threats to ecosystems, human well-being, and sustainable development worldwide. This study explores the connections between Green Leadership (GL) and Sustainable Consumption Behavior (SCB) with the mediating role of employees' Pro-environmental Behavior (PEB) and Green Literacy (GLiT). The study is conducted in the Banking Sector of Pakistan. Data was collected from banking employees having a significant impact on the environment. A quantitative survey was adopted depending on the research team personnel connections and relationships. The survey was conducted through distribution of online questionnaire to banking sector employees in major cities of Pakistan. We have collected data from 476 banks employees using convenience sampling. Smart PLS was used to analyze collected data. "Structural Equation Modeling" (SEM) was employed so that the justified relationships with mediating effects of employees' Pro-environmental behavior and Green Literacy could be explored and evaluated. The relationship of Green Leadership (GL) and Sustainable Consumption Behavior (SCB) with the mediating role of employees' Pro-environmental Behavior (PEB) and Green Literacy (GLiT) has been accepted.

Keywords: Green Leadership, Green Literacy, Pro-environmental Behavior, Green Consumption Behavior

1. Introduction

Climate change, biodiversity loss, deforestation, and pollution have become critical threats to the sustainability of our planet. These environmental crises are largely driven by unsustainable industrial practices, excessive resource consumption, and weak environmental regulations in many parts of the world. Environmental degradation involves the depletion of natural resources through the use of a lot of paper which degrades the natural resources and the use of plastics that have negative impacts on wildlife and hence expose us to disaster and scarcity of resources (Xuerong & Seoki, 2021). Global environmental degradation has reached alarming levels, with the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) reporting that global temperatures are expected to rise by 1.5°C as early as 2030 if current emission trends continue.

In this regard, it is necessary to find the role of all industries and business to protect the environment. Understanding how banks respond to environmental concerns is vital in shaping policies that align economic growth with ecological preservation (Burhanudin et al., 2021; Nawaz Khan, 2022). The employees who are aware of the impacts of their work on the environment are more likely to embrace environmentally friendly behaviors which may encourage the financial institutions to embrace good green cultures (Burhanudin et al., 2021). Leaders may use this to persuade their followers to adopt environmental responsibility, which will benefit the entire organization (Saleem et al., 2020).

Green leadership, in according to Egri and Herman, 2000 is a leadership process which involves and enables individuals and organizations to work together towards a shared vision of sustainable use of natural resources. The leader's role in driving environmental responsibility and introducing sustainability is highlighted. Based on the integration models of organizational and institutional behavior, leaders and team members can be evaluated through their performance (job performance) which can impact the organizational output in a positive or negative manner (Nawaz Khan, 2022).

In line with the concepts of Pro-environmental behavior (PEB) by Li et al. (2020) and Lange and Dewitte (2019), PEB is constituted of actions that people take to reduce their negative

impacts on the environment or to increase their positive contribution to the natural environment. In the organizational environment the PEB must also encompass behaviors that can be objectively measured in the workplace, such as recycling, conserving paper, water and electricity (Robertson & Barling, 2013). These behaviors are key to influencing ecological outcomes because they help to change environmental structures and processes to facilitate and support more access to and effective use of resources, such as energy and materials (Stern, 2000).

Green literacy is defined as an individual's ability to comprehend environmental problems and adopt actions that show concern for the environment and recognize the effects of human activities on it. It has become a highlighted skill for developing people that can make well-informed choices and take suitable actions that can contribute to culture of sustainability (Liu & Tobias, 2024; Law et al., 2023). Green literacy is not just about raising environmental awareness; it also aids the implementation of sustainable practices in everyday life. It includes, for example, green technology, responsible consumption, marketing of eco-friendly products and services (Beny et al., 2023).

The concept of sustainable consumption in connection to the circular economy has been defined in a number of research (De Guimarães, 2023; Shevchenko et al., 2023). To sum up, a few of the findings have been environmental concerns, attitude of the individual, perceived social pressure, and economic receptivity (; Ur Rahman et al. 2023; Durrani et al. 2023).

Although the concept of sustainability is becoming increasingly popular (Kardoyo et al., 2022; Li et al., 2020) most of the literature focuses on the direct impact of leadership on environmental outcomes (Kardoyo et al., 2022; Egri and Herman, 2000) and does not consider the psychological and knowledge-based mechanisms that might explain this influence. Although green leadership has been related with pro-environmental behaviors and sustainable outcomes (Arici & Uysal, 2022; Han et al., 2019), few studies have focused on the double mediating effect of pro-environmental behavior and green literacy in understanding the link between green leadership and sustainable consumption behavior (Li et al., 2022; Mukherjee et al., 2016; Smol et al., 2018). Moreover, the current research often examines these between variables individually, without embedding them in a larger and more comprehensive framework that encompasses the interaction between these variables.

This leaves a large body of research to be filled with understanding the interplays between cognitive (green literacy) and behavioral (pro-environmental behavior) pathways of green leadership to contribute to sustainability. In view of this gap, this study proposes an integrated model that investigates the simultaneous mediating role of pro-environmental behavior and the green literacy and thus contributes to the better understanding of the influence of green leadership on sustainable consumption behavior.

This is especially true because corporations are under a lot of pressure to become ecologically sustainable due to environmental issues (Li et al., 2020; Egri and Herman, 2000). Organizations are adopting green policies and practices more often in an effort to boost economic value and enhance environmental outcomes. This study is crucial to comprehending how environmentally conscious leaders and managers may motivate their employees to make the required changes in their consumption habits (Arici & Uysal, 2022; Han et al., 2019). The study shows how people's degree of environmentalism or green literacy, as well as their actual eco-friendly acts, serve as a conduit through which green leadership may encourage sustainable consumption by looking at pro-environmental behavior and green literacy as mediators.

The proposed framework is based on Ajzen's (1991) Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), which holds that attitudes, subjective standards, and perceived behavioral control all influence behavior. In the context of environmental sustainability, green leadership can be viewed as an important antecedent that shapes employees' environmental attitudes and

normative beliefs by promoting environmental values, ethical conduct, and sustainable practices within organizations. Through role modeling and environmental advocacy, green leaders encourage employees to engage in pro-environmental behavior and enhance their green literacy. Pro-environmental behavior reflects favorable attitudes toward environmental protection, whereas green literacy increases individuals' knowledge and perceived capability to make environmentally responsible decisions. According to TPB, positive environmental attitudes and greater perceived behavioral control increase the likelihood of engaging in sustainable behaviors (Ajzen, 1991; Bosnjak et al., 2020). Consequently, employees who exhibit stronger pro-environmental behavior and possess higher levels of green literacy are more likely to adopt sustainable consumption behaviors. Therefore, pro-environmental behavior and green literacy serve as key mechanisms through which green leadership influences sustainable consumption behavior, consistent with the propositions of TPB.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Green Leadership and Pro-environmental Behavior

“Leader’s ability to mobilize individuals and organizations toward a long-term vision of sustainable use of natural resource referred as green leadership” (Egri & Herman, 2000). Drawing on organizational behavior models, leadership effectiveness can be evaluated through both outcomes (job performance) and behaviors that either support or hinder organizational goals (Cooper, 2022). Leaders play a critical role in influencing employees and stakeholders to adopt environmentally friendly initiatives and align with broader climate and sustainability agendas (Kardoyo et al., 2022). In line with this perspective, green leadership is more specific in the sense that it focuses interests of the followers and leads them with an inherent motivation of protecting followers’ needs (Liden et al., 2014), and exemplifies altruistic care, love and compassionate purpose (Van Dierendonck, 2011). Moreover, green leaders give resources, guidance and support to employees which increases their perceived behavioral control and thus they feel more able to participate in pro-environmental behaviors (PEBs) (Afsar et al., 2016; Li et al., 2020; Robertson & Carleton, 2018).

Furthermore, pro-environmental behaviors (PEBs) are defined as deliberate actions aimed at minimizing environmental harm and promoting sustainability (Li et al., 2020; Lange Dewitte, 2019). These behaviors include activities such as recycling, conserving resources (e.g., water, energy, paper), and avoiding environmentally harmful practices (Robertson & Barling, 2013). PEBs are also conceptualized as actions that positively influence ecosystems by enhancing resource availability (Stern, 2000). Within organizations, employee PEBs contribute significantly to sustainability objectives, organizational efficiency, improved brand image, and competitive advantage (Li et al., 2020; Ku et al., 2020).

With the lens of the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) by (Ajzen 1991), individual behavior is influenced by attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. Green leadership is one way of influencing positive attitudes towards environmental sustainability among employees by emphasizing its value and benefits. Meanwhile, leaders set high subjective norms by setting up organizational norms of environmental responsibility. Previous research has confirmed that leadership is a significant determinant of employees' engagement in PEB (Afsar et al., 2016; Li et al., 2020; Robertson & Carleton, 2018); as well as awareness and behavioral control are among the most salient determinants of pro-environmental intentions and actions (Arkorfol et al., 2023; Savari et al., 2023). As a result, green leadership fosters employees' intentions to act and their actual engagement in pro-environmental behaviors. However, prior studies indicate that leadership style is a key determinant influencing employee engagement in PEB (Afsar et al., 2016; Li et al., 2020;

Robertson & Carleton, 2018; Scherbaum et al., 2008). Hence, subsequent hypothesis is proposed:

H1: *Green leadership has positive effects on pro-environmental behavior.*

2.2 Green Leadership and Green Literacy

Green literacy is increasingly documented as a grave factor in fostering environmentally responsible behavior around the globe in current era. It refers to individuals' understanding of environmental concepts and awareness of the impact of human activities on ecosystems, enabling informed decision-making and sustainable actions (Liu & Tobias, 2024; Law et al., 2023). Complementarily, financial literacy has been linked to sustainable consumption, as it enables individuals to make environmentally responsible financial decisions, such as investing in green technologies and supporting eco-friendly products (Beny et al., 2023).

According to Berniak-Wońny and Rataj (2023), green leadership is characterized by leaders' dedication to environmental stewardship, social and environmental obligations, and strategic financial sustainability. By adopting eco-friendly behaviors and practices, increasing environmental awareness and education, and assisting in the creation of green-oriented policies and decision-making, green leadership fosters green literacy. According to Liu and Tobias (2024), green literacy also involves assessing human and ecological systems and addressing the need to adopt sustainable practices.

Green leadership has an effect on green literacy through attitude, intention, and behavior of the employees, which are critical factors in the green environment also supported by the Theory of Planned Behavior by (Ajzen1991). The theory suggests that attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived control over behavior play a role in the organization's behavior. Green leaders establish positive environmental attitudes through their actions of demonstrating their commitment to sustainability and build encouraging social norms that promote environmentally responsible behavior in organizations (Egri & Herman, 2000; Kardoyo et al., 2022). Furthermore, leaders can foster employees' perceived control over green behaviors by providing them with knowledge, resources and guidance. Thus, the personnel get to be informed and aware, and can make sustainable decisions, thus enhancing their green literacy.

H2: *Green leadership has positive effects on affects green literacy.*

2.3 Pro-Environmental Behavior and Sustainable Consumption Behavior

Sustainable consumption behaviors are closely associated with circular economy principles, including reducing resource use, reusing products, and recycling materials (De Guimarães, 2023; Shevchenko et al., 2023). These practices promote extended product lifecycles and efficient resource utilization (Sun et al., 2023). Key drivers of sustainable consumption include environmental concern, individual attitudes, social norms, and economic considerations (Durrani et al., 2023; Ur Rahman et al., 2023). Moreover, pro-environmental identity has emerged as a significant predictor of sustainable behavior (Mayer & Carter, 2024; Wyss et al., 2022). Knowledge, attitude, and intention are as environmental factor that, according to Hamzah and Tanwi (2021) are the primary drivers of pro-environmental behavior. Pro- environmental attitudes are also reflected through decision and behaviors to conserve the environment (Karpudewan, 2021).

Pro-environmental behavior is a key element in the formation of sustainable consumption behavior, as when individuals are actively involved in pro-environmental action, they are more likely to engage in sustainable consumption behavior (De Guimarães, 2023; Sun et al., 2023). Energy saving, waste reduction, and environmentally conscious decision-making are examples of such behaviors which are directly linked to an individual's environmental values and awareness, which in turn affects his/her consumption decisions (Sun et al., 2023; Karpudewan, 2021). People's established habits and attitudes result from their repeated engagement in pro-environmental behaviors, which in turn lead them to use sustainable

products, use resources responsibly, and reduce environmental impact. Furthermore, pro-environmental behaviour can act as a behavioural base which helps to turn environmental concern into concrete consumption behaviour, thus paving the way for long-term sustainability (Mayer & Carter, 2024; Wyss et al., 2022). Thus, those who show higher scores on pro-environmental behavior will be more likely to display sustainable consumption behavior, which further enhances the connection between environmental responsibility and sustainable lifestyle choices.

“TPB” as employed in (Ajzen1991), explained that when they perceive a behavior as beneficial, it is appropriate for their attitudes, social norms, and sense of control (Shalender & Sharma, 2021). In the context of sustainable consumption, prior research has focused on understanding current consumption patterns and the factors contributing to their effectiveness, particularly in reducing the use of natural resources, minimizing toxic material production, and lowering waste and pollutant emissions throughout a product’s lifecycle (Quoquab & Mohammad, 2020; Akenji & Bengtsson, 2014). Based on TPB, these attitudes and behaviors collectively strengthen individuals’ intentions to act sustainably, thereby supporting the hypothesis that

H3: *Pro-environmental behavior has positive effects on sustainable consumption behavior.*

2.4 Green Literacy and Sustainable Consumption Behavior

Education for sustainable consumption (ESC) emphasizes the role of individuals as key actors in promoting sustainability (Sahakian & Seyfang, 2018; Lin et al., 2012). In this regard, green literacy plays a significant role in fostering sustainable development and responsible consumption practices. Concurrently, there is growing societal concern regarding environmental issues and the use of green products. Consumers with higher green awareness tend to adjust their consumption patterns by increasing the use of environmentally friendly goods and services to offset the negative impacts of conventional products (Lin et al., 2012). Haws et al. (2014) argued that stronger green values enhance consumers’ preferences for sustainable products, with social and recognition values further attracting consumers toward green choices (Mohd Suki & Mohd Suki, 2015). Moreover, studies indicate that environmental concern has become a norm, with green consumer behavior increasingly expected (Chatterjee et al., 2022). However, prior research has predominantly measured green consumption through the purchase of green products, particularly home appliances (Li et al., 2021; Xin & Long, 2019).

Green literacy is associated with positive impacts on sustainable consumption based on Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) by Ajzen (1991), which states people’s attitudes, beliefs, and perceptions of self-control affect behavior. People who have higher green literacy have higher environmental knowledge and environmental awareness and have brought positive attitudes to green consumption (Tran et al., 2024; Rahmanian et al., 2024). This knowledge also increases their capacity to assess the environmental implications of their decision, which will increase perceived behavioral control.

Furthermore, the people with better green literacy tend to have positive intentions to consume sustainably (Liu & Tobias, 2024; Law et al., 2023) and also are more likely to take action when they have a positive intention. It is found that those with higher green literacy are more likely to form positive intention to consume sustainably, and also more likely to take action if they have positive intention. Hence, green literacy is a key element for sustainable consumption.

H4: *Green literacy has positive effects on sustainable consumption behavior.*

2.5 Pro-Environmental Behavior serve as a Mediator in the Relationship Between Green Leadership and Sustainable Consumption Behavior

Green leadership emphasizes environmentally responsible decision-making and the promotion of sustainable practices within organizations (Arici & Uysal, 2022). Green

leadership plays a fundamental role in shaping environmentally responsible outcomes by promoting sustainability-oriented values and practices within organizations. Leaders who demonstrate commitment to environmental stewardship influence followers to adopt eco-friendly behaviors through role modeling, communication, and supportive policies (Han et al., 2019). As a result, employees are encouraged to engage in pro-environmental behavior, which reflects their active participation in environmentally responsible actions such as recycling, waste reduction, and the use of sustainable resources. Behavioral models, including the pro-environmental behavior framework (Kollmuss & Agyeman, 2002), highlight that such behaviors are driven by individuals' knowledge, awareness, values, and attitudes toward the environment. Empirical evidence further suggests that increased environmental awareness enhances the likelihood of engaging in these sustainable practices (Kousar et al., 2022).

Pro-environmental behavior is a key mediating variable between green leadership and sustainable consumption behavior. Green leadership creates an organizational culture and environment that emphasize the importance of environmental responsibility, promoting eco-friendly attitudes and behaviors among employees (Kollmuss & Agyeman, 2002; Han et al., 2019). Leaders, through role modelling, support and environmental values promotion, encourage employees to practice pro-environment activities like resource conservation, reduction of waste and environmentally conscious decision making. Such behaviors, in turn, manifest themselves in sustainable consumption, wherein people make consumption choices in a way that is consistent with their environmental goals (Afsar et al., 2016; Li et al., 2020). Therefore, pro-environmental behavior is identified as a behavioral pathway that indirectly contributes to sustainable consumption behavior, playing an important role in the linkage between green leadership and sustainable consumption behavior.

Pro-environmental behavior, in turn, leads to sustainable consumption behavior, as individuals translate their environmental concerns into responsible consumption choices, including the adoption of eco-friendly products and reduced resource usage (Arkorful et al., 2023). This progression of influence from leadership to action and ultimately to consumption is a model that is consistent with the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) (Ajzen, 1991), which posits that attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived control over behavior influence individuals' intentions and behaviors. Green leadership fosters positive attitudes and norms, pro-environmental behavior reflects the enactment of these intentions, and sustainable consumption represents the final behavioral outcome.

Therefore, pro-environmental behavior serves as a crucial mediating mechanism linking green leadership with sustainable consumption behavior.

H5: Pro-environmental behavior mediated the relationship between green leadership and sustainable consumption behavior

2.6 Green Literacy Mediates the Relationship Between Green Leadership and Sustainable Consumption Behavior

Green leadership plays a pivotal role in promoting environmental sustainability by encouraging awareness, education, and responsible environmental practices among individuals. Through their commitment to sustainability and role modeling, green leaders influence individuals to adopt green attitudes and behaviors (Han et al., 2019). Such leadership fosters an environment where individuals become more aware of environmental issues and are motivated to support green initiatives, invest in environmental solutions, and engage in practices such as waste sorting (Li et al., 2022; Mukherjee et al., 2016). In this way, green leadership contributes significantly to the development of green literacy.

Green literacy promotes the level of awareness that enables individuals to understand and evaluate their impact on the environment. It enhances individuals' ability to critically assess environmental information and make informed, green decisions (Smol et al., 2018). By

promoting sustainability awareness, green literacy encourages individuals to adopt environmentally responsible behaviors and increases the likelihood of behavioral change (Han et al., 2019).

Green literacy is an important mechanism in the relationship between green leadership and sustainable consumption behavior. Green leadership creates an organization culture where environmental awareness, learning and sharing are encouraged, adding to the awareness among the members of the organization of environmental issues and environmental sustainability (Berniak-WoŃny and Rataj, 2023; Liu & Tobias, 2024; Law et al., 2023). Leaders foster green literacy among employees by promoting the values of the environment, communicating and training them. This heightened awareness and knowledge of the environment then impacts upon consumer decisions, leading to a preference for sustainable products, a decrease in resource use, and environment-friendly practices (Sahakian & Seyfang, 2018; Lin et al., 2012). Hence, the importance of green literacy as a cognitive pathway that indirectly lies behind sustainable consumption behavior, which makes green leadership a bridge between leadership influence and informed and sustainable decision-making processes.

The relationship among green leadership, green literacy, and sustainable consumption behavior can be explained through the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) by (Ajzen 1991) According to TPB by (Ajzen 1991), behavior is shaped by attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. Green leadership fosters supportive norms and positive attitudes, while green literacy enhances individuals' knowledge and perceived control over making environmentally responsible decisions. As a result, green literacy leads to sustainable consumption behavior, as individuals become more conscious of their consumption choices and shift toward environmentally friendly products and practices. It fosters greater adoption of sustainable lifestyles and increases the use of eco-friendly practices (Beny et al., 2023). Therefore, green literacy acts as a key mediating mechanism through which green leadership influences sustainable consumption behavior, ultimately fostering a transition toward environmental sustainability (Liu & Tobias, 2024; Law et al., 2023).

H6: Green literacy mediated the relationship between green leadership and sustainable consumption behavior

Figure 2.1 Theoretical Framework

3. Research Methodology

The research methodology is important in establishing the valid, reliable, and generalizable outcomes of a research study. The method used in this study is quantitative research method, because this method has become widely used in the social sciences that it can test the hypothesis with statistical analysis. The advantages it offers justify its selection as an approach, as it limits researcher bias, increases the generalizability of findings, and boosts the reliability of the procedure (Schmid et al., 2024). Relationships among variables are especially well examined by quantitative methods, which are structured and objective in nature.

Moreover, this study uses a cross-sectional research design that involves collecting data from respondents at one time (Robinson et al., 2005). This design is suitable for the study of relationships between variables when the study environment cannot be manipulated. Survey methods were employed for data collection as it enables the researchers for the collection of data from a very wide range of people, make it possible to carry out statistical testing and assess the reliability and validity of measurement (White, et al., 2005).

The data was gathered from the employees of banking sector in Pakistan. Initially, a total 750 respondents from different banks located in major cities of Lahore, Sahiwal, Multan, Dera Ghazi Khan, Sukkur and Karachi participated in the study. Data collection took place from May to July 2025. Of the 525 questionnaires returned, 70% were complete. Data screening resulted in 49 questionnaires being discarded due to large numbers of missing data and incompleteness. Finally, the number of usable responses that were obtained was 476 (63.64% valid response rate), which is adequate for statistical analysis in behavioral research.

In organizational and behavioral research, the use of survey-based quantitative research is largely accepted due to its methodological rigor, especially when studying the relationships between leadership styles and employee attitudes and behavioral outcomes. Creswell and Creswell (2018) state that quantitative survey designs work well in determining patterns and testing theoretical models in large populations. Likewise, Saunders et al. (2019) point out that cross-sectional surveys are especially valuable when the data is required to be gathered quickly in a relatively short period of time, but without sacrificing statistical strength.

3.1 Population and Sample

In addition, this study is conducted in the context of the banking sector in Pakistan because of the well-organized nature of banking organization and the growing focus on sustainability and employee behavior in the banking sector. The importance of service-sector industries for studying behavioral constructs like pro-environmental behavior and sustainable consumption practices has been emphasized in previous studies, as service employees can directly affect the environmental performance of their organizations (Saeed et al., 2021; Khan et al., 2022). Hence, the chosen context of population brings the study to the practical as well as theoretical relevance.

Sample was drawn from the targeted population on the basis of convenience sampling technique opted for the study. Convenience sampling technique was opted because bank employees normally have to follow strict confidential policies, hard working hours and time constraints. So, to reach required sample size, convenience sampling was most appropriate to add respondents who are willing and accessible.

3.2 Instrument Development

The final version of the questionnaire was created using a Google form to directly gather data from the respondents, and the research scales were taken from earlier studies. The demographic questions are in the first section, and the Likert-only questions are in the

second. After filling out the initial response, the respondent's following response was limited. Since the data was gathered in a methodical manner and presented for additional analysis, there was no need for additional data filtering. The following measures were taken for the collecting information about the constructs of the study.

Table: 1 Details of Scales

Constructs	Items	Source
Green Leadership	11	Egri and Herman, 2000
Pro-environmental Behaviors	5	Dunlap et al., 2000
Green Literacy	5	Kaiser and Fuhrer, 2003
Sustainable Consumption Behaviors	5	Peattie, 2010; Young et al., 2010

Source: Developed by researcher

4. Results

4.1 Demographic Statistics

The demographic profile of the research participants is included in this section. This section adds details on the respondents' age, gender, education, experience, and job title. SPSS software is used for analysis.

Table 2: Demographic profiles of the respondents.

Gender of Respondents		percentage
Man	418	87.81
Female	58	12.19
Age of Respondents		
18-22	54	
23-27	136	
28-32	262	
33 & above	24	
Qualification of Respondents		
Matric	003	0.83
Intermediate	071	15.12
Bachelors	332	69.96
Masters	047	10.07
MPhil or PhD	018	03.98

Source: SPSS output

The majority of respondents almost 87.81% are male and 12.19 percent are female. The age group of 18 to 22 years old has the majority of responders, while the age group of 23 to 27 years old has the second-highest number. The age ranges of 28–32 and 33 and older have very few responders. The majority of respondents 69.96% belong to the educational group of graduates, followed by a group of intermediates (15.13 percent). The third largest group of respondents, based on educational level, are those with master's level education (10.08 percent), followed by M. Phil and above level respondents (4 percent). Since job title is regarded as a primary indication in the list of demographic variables, it is used as a demographic variable in this study. Every variable satisfies the normality assumption. Table 3 shows that skewness spans from -0.7 to 2.358, which is less than ± 2.58 , whereas kurtosis runs from -1.31 to 2.501 (Hair et al. 2014).

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of Variables

Items	Mean	Media n	Min	Max	St. Dev	Skew	Kurtosi s
GL1	3.785	4.000	1.000	5.000	0.952	1.564	-1.099
GL2	3.715	4.000	1.000	5.000	0.863	1.782	-1.187
GL3	3.599	4.000	1.000	5.000	0.867	0.756	-0.710
GL4	3.756	4.000	1.000	5.000	0.973	0.602	-0.750
GL5	3.820	4.000	1.000	5.000	0.840	1.453	-0.830
GL6	3.596	4.000	1.000	5.000	0.833	0.016	-0.670
GL7	3.744	4.000	1.000	5.000	0.911	0.002	-0.375
GL8	3.634	4.000	1.000	5.000	0.997	-0.149	-0.594
GL9	3.703	4.000	1.000	5.000	0.991	0.626	-0.854
GL10	3.802	4.000	1.000	5.000	0.953	0.790	-0.870
GL1	3.701	4.000	1.000	5.000	0.994	0.792	-0.921
GLT2	3.756	4.000	1.000	5.000	0.930	0.597	-0.846
GLT3	3.509	3.000	1.000	5.000	0.955	0.005	-0.065

GLT4	3.503	4.000	1.000	5.000	1.151	0.185	-1.069
GLT5	3.410	4.000	1.000	5.000	0.996	0.479	-0.858
PEA1	3.584	4.000	1.000	5.000	1.022	0.617	-1.016
PEA2	3.235	4.000	1.000	5.000	1.159	-0.660	-0.559
PEA3	3.206	3.000	1.000	5.000	1.194	-0.463	-0.662
SCB1	3.730	4.000	1.000	5.000	0.882	0.549	-0.718
SCB2	3.721	4.000	1.000	5.000	0.939	-0.226	-0.306
SCB3	3.535	4.000	1.000	5.000	0.939	0.122	-0.682
SCB4	3.596	4.000	1.000	5.000	0.916	0.761	-0.957

Source: PLS output

4.2 Multicollinearity Test

According to Hair et al. (2011), multicollinearity refers to a condition in which two or more exogenous variables are highly correlated, potentially distorting the estimation of regression coefficients. To assess multicollinearity, the variance inflation factor (VIF) is widely regarded as a reliable statistical indicator, with a commonly accepted threshold value of less than 5 (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2016). In the present study, the VIF values for green leadership (GL) range from 1.643 to 2.455, for green literacy (GLit) from 1.135 to 2.072, for pro-environmental behavior (PEB) from 1.053 to 1.657, and for sustainable consumption behavior (SCB) from 1.305 to 1.488. As all VIF values fall well below the recommended threshold, the results indicate the absence of multicollinearity issues, thereby confirming that the data are suitable for further statistical analyses.

4.3 Confirmatory Factor Analysis

This section reports the results derived from the confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) performed in this study. The analysis was carried out using SmartPLS 4.0, utilizing its built-in CFA functionality. As noted by Ishtiaq (2019), a minimum sample size of 150 is considered adequate for conducting CFA, which supports the appropriateness of the sample used in this research.

The results of the confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) utilizing the principal component analysis method for the current investigation are shown in this section of the outcome analysis. Only confirmatory factor analysis, using the built-in CFA function of SmartPLS 4.0, was carried out in this work. Ishtiaq (2019) recommends that a minimum sample size of 150 be used for CFA. The factors loadings, an output of the PLS Algorithm, are used to determine the CFA outcomes in the next section.

4.4 Assessment of Path Model (PLS-SEM)

Figure 4.1: PLS Path Model Assessment

The measurement model (also called the outer model) is used to assess the validity and reliability of the instruments used in the study to ensure the constructs are correctly measured by their respective indicators. The evaluation of the outer model typically involves three key approaches to reliability assessment: construct reliability, coefficient alpha (Cronbach's alpha) reliability, and indicator (item) reliability. In addition, the Fornell and Larcker (1981) criterion is widely applied to assess both convergent and discriminant validity of the constructs.

In the context of PLS-SEM path modeling, latent constructs are commonly represented by rectangles, whereas observed variables or indicators (manifest variables) are depicted as circles. These indicators may be reflective or formative in nature, depending on the model specification. The comprehensive evaluation of the measurement model is discussed in Section 4.6 of the guidelines and is summarized here for clarity.

Specifically, outer model assessment focuses on examining the reliability and validity of the constructs. According to Vinzi et al. (2013), acceptable outer loading values should be at least 0.50. Indicators with outer loadings below this threshold are recommended to be removed, beginning with those exhibiting the lowest values, in order to improve the overall quality of the measurement model. This approach is further supported by Hair et al. (2014), who argue that such refinement enhances the robustness of the data. Furthermore, the outer model assessment includes the evaluation of individual item reliability, internal consistency reliability, content validity, convergent validity, and discriminant validity, as emphasized by Hair et al. (2011) and Henseler et al. (2015).

4.4.1 Individual Item Reliability

Before proceeding with the convergent validity of the outer model, the loading and cross loading of the variables are examined. Convergent validity also known as discriminant validity is a measure of criteria suggested by Hair, et al., (2014) thus for an item to qualify for the convergent validity; it is expected that the factor load should be greater than 0.7, very few must less than 0.6, furthermore none of the other constructs' items should have a loading greater than the correct construct.

4.4.2 Internal Consistency Reliability

The degree to which each item in a particular subscale evaluates the same concept is known as internal consistency dependability. According to Hair et al. (2011), composite dependability should be at least 0.6 and the required AVE should be at least 0.5. The measurement model is dedicated to further research since all of the variables are very reliable and the AVE values above the 0.50 threshold, as seen in Table 4. The internal consistency of the constructs is further investigated by computing the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient. According to George and Malley (2019), a score of 0.9 or above is considered extraordinary, a score of 0.8 is considered good, and a score of 0.7 or below is considered acceptable. Table below displays the calculated composite reliability, Cronbach's Alpha, and AVE for each variable.

Table 4 Construct Reliability, Cronbach's Alpha, Composite Reliability and AVE of all the Latent Variables

Variable Name	Items	Factors Loadings	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Extracted (AVE)	Variance
Sustainable	SC	0.772	0.903	0.907	0.919	
	B1					
Consumption	SC	0.721				
	B2					

Behavior	SC	0.751			
	B3				
	SC	0.749			
	B4				
	SC	0.697			
	B5				
	SC	0.671			
	B6				
	SC	0.688			
	B7				
	SC	0.751			
B8					
SC	0.696				
B9					
SC	0.691				
B10					
SC	0.793				
B11					
Green Leadership	GL	1.777	0.784	0.737	0.808
	1				
	GL	2.117			
	2				
	GL	2.441			
	3				
	GL	2.013			
4					
GL	1.810				
5					
GL	2.613				
6					
GL	1.194				
7					
Green Literacy	GL	1.135	0.793	0.748	0.751
	T1				
	GL	2.072			
	T2				
GL	1.991				
T3					
Pro-Environmental	PE1	1.053	0.807	0.790	0.805
	PE2	1.606			
	PE3	1.657			
	PE4	1.488			
	PE5	1.347			
	PE6	1.305			
	PE7	1.336			
	PE8	1.053			

Source: PLS output

Table above display the values of Cronbach's Alpha, loadings of factors, the composite reliability, and average variance retrieved from the constructs of the study. Since all of

the values are higher than the threshold values, each individual construct's dependability requirements are met.

4.4.3 Discriminant Validity

Table 5: Matrix of Discriminant Validity (Fornell-Larcker Criterion)

Variables	GL	GLT	PEA	SCB
Green Leadership	0.713			
Geen Literacy	0.613	0.722		
Pro-Environment Behavior	0.473	0.707	0.710	
Sustainable Consumption Behavior	0.733	0.604	0.374	0.712

Source: PLS output

Table 5 reports the results of the discriminant validity assessment. The findings show that the square root of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE), presented on the diagonal in bold, is higher than the correlations between constructs. This confirms that the Fornell and Larcker (1981) criterion for discriminant validity is met, indicating that each construct explains more variance in its own indicators than in other constructs within the model.

In addition, discriminant validity was assessed using the Heterotrait–Monotrait (HTMT) ratio, as recommended by Henseler, Ringle, and Sarstedt (2015). The HTMT approach is considered a more rigorous and reliable method for evaluating discriminant validity in PLS-SEM compared to traditional techniques such as the Fornell–Larcker criterion and cross-loadings, which may fail to detect issues in certain situations. The HTMT values presented in Table 5 are below the recommended threshold of 0.90 (and well below 1.00), indicating that the constructs are empirically distinct.

Moreover, the confidence intervals associated with HTMT do not exceed the threshold value of 1.0, further confirming the absence of discriminant validity problems. Overall, these results demonstrate that all latent variables in the model meet the required standards of discriminant validity in accordance with the guidelines of Henseler et al. (2015).

Table 6: The R-square and adjusted R-square values for dependent variables

	R-square	R-square adjusted
GLit	.63	.63
PEB	.22	.22
SCB	.53	.53

Source: PLS output

The R-square values for Intention to Consume Green Literacy and Pro-Environmental behavior are 0.63 and 0.22, respectively, in Table 6. This indicates that the sustainable consumption behavior may alter the sustainable consumption behavior of employees approximately 51%. Pro-environmental behavior also be changed by 53% , and green literacy 63%.

Table 7: The correlations coefficients

Co-relations	Correlation Coefficient
GL->SCB	.698
PEA->GLT	.975
SCB-> GLT	.733

Source: PLS output

Table 7 display the relationships between the constructs of the study as well as the correlation values for each relationship. All of the relationships aside from the one

between gender and subjective norms are shown to be substantially connected based on the correlation values mentioned above.

4.5 Structural Model

Once the validity and reliability of the measurement model have been established, the outcome of the structural model analysis are presented in the following section. The inner model in PLS-SEM is estimated using the explicitly specified structural connection of variables, and the t-values of each structural route are provided as coefficients. The theorized structural linkages in a research model function as the structure's central component, according to Hair et al. (2011). The t-values are computed using the bootstrapped approach following 5000 sample iterations with 476 case observations. As Hair et al. (2014) stated, bootstrapping may be used as a proxy for standard error.

Table 8: Direct effects results

Relations	B	(STD EV)	T statistics	P values	Decision
“Green Leadership -> Pro-Environmental Behavior”	0.48	0.04	11.70	.000	Supported
“Green Leadership -> Green Literacy”	0.73	0.03	09.31	.000	Supported
“Pro-Environmental Behavior->sustainable consumption behavior”	0.55	0.04	13.80	.000	Supported
“Green Literacy -> sustainable consumption behavior”	0.39	0.03	10.66	.000	Supported

Source: PLS output

The results presented in Table 8 indicate that green leadership is positively and significantly associated with pro-environmental behavior (PEB), as evidenced by a beta coefficient of 0.040, a t-value of 11.702, and a p-value of 0.000. These results confirm that green leadership has a significant positive effect on employees’ pro-environmental behavior.

In a similar vein, green leadership is also significantly and positively related to sustainable consumption behavior (SCB), with a beta value of 0.34, a t-value of 9.317, and a p-value of 0.000. This indicates that stronger green leadership is associated with higher levels of sustainable consumption practices among employees.

In addition, the results reveal a significant positive association between green literacy and pro-environmental behavior, with a beta coefficient of 0.041, a t-value of 13.809, and a p-value of 0.000. This indicates that higher levels of green literacy are linked with increased engagement in pro-environmental behaviors. A further significant relationship is observed between green literacy and sustainable consumption behavior, as reflected by a beta value of 0.037, a t-value of 10.669, and a p-value of 0.000, demonstrating a positive and statistically significant effect.

Moreover, the assessment of multicollinearity indicates that all variance inflation factor (VIF) values fall below the acceptable threshold, confirming that no critical multicollinearity issues exist among the exogenous constructs. This suggests that the predictor variables are sufficiently independent and do not exhibit problematic intercorrelations. Although high correlations among constructs may indicate redundancy and potential inflation of effects, the current results do not suggest such concerns.

Furthermore, prior literature emphasizes that multicollinearity among independent latent constructs can significantly distort statistical inference by inflating standard errors and reducing the statistical significance of regression coefficients (Perrini & Tencati, 2006; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2016). Therefore, the absence of multicollinearity in the present study supports the robustness and reliability of the estimated model parameters.

Table 9: Results of hypothesis testing (Mediating effects)

	(STDEV)	T statistics	P values	Decision
GL -> PEB -> SCB	0.291 0.034	8.583	0.000	Full Mediation
GL -> GLit -> SCB	0.269 0.029	9.179	0.000	Full Mediation

Source: PLS output

Table 9, along with Figures 4.3 and 4.4, illustrates a significant mediating role of green leadership within the relationship between green literacy among employees and sustainable consumption behavior. The results show a beta coefficient of 0.034, a t-value of 8.583, and a p-value of 0.000, indicating a significant full mediation effect. In addition, a second mediation analysis reveals that pro-environmental behavior also acts as a mediator in the relationship between green leadership, green literacy, and sustainable consumption behavior. This indirect effect is supported by a beta value of 0.029, a t-value of 9.719, and a p-value of 0.000, confirming a statistically significant mediation effect.

Figure 4.3 Bootstrapping Mediation Analysis

Figure 4.4 Bootstrapping Mediation Analysis

Table: 10 Hypothesis Results

Sr. No.	Hypotheses	Accepted/Rejected
1	“Green leadership has positive effects on pro-environmental behavior.	Accepted
2	Green leadership has positive effects on green literacy.	Accepted
3	Pro-environmental behavior has positive effects on sustainable consumption.	Accepted
4	Green literacy has positive effects on sustainable consumption.	Accepted
5	Pro-environmental behavior mediated the relationship between green leadership and sustainable consumption.	Accepted
6	Green literacy mediated the relationship between green leadership and sustainable consumption.”	Accepted

Source: Prepared by researcher

Green leadership and pro-environmental behavior are significantly related, with a beta value of 0.040, a t-value of 11.702, and a p-value of 0.000. The relationship between green leadership and green literacy is also positive and significant, indicated by a beta coefficient of 0.34, a t-value of 9.317, and a p-value of 0.000. Furthermore, pro-environmental behavior shows a strong positive association with sustainable consumption behavior, as reflected by a beta value of 0.041, a t-value of 13.809, and a p-value of 0.000. Overall, the t-values and p-values confirm that all relationships are statistically significant.

The results show a strong correlation between green literacy and sustainable consumption behavior, with a beta of 0.037, a t-value of 10.669, and a p-value of 0.000. With a beta value of 0.034, a t-value of 8.583, and a p-value of 0.000, the mediation effect of Green Leadership between Green Literacy and Sustainable Consumption Behavior is significant. With a beta value of 0.029, a t-value of 9.719, and a p-value of 0.000, the second mediation is the mediating effect Pro-Environmental, which mediates the link between Green Leadership, Green Literacy, and sustainable consumption behavior.

5. Discussion of Results

Green leadership focuses on prioritizing followers’ needs and guiding them through an

intrinsic motivation to protect environment (Liden et al., 2014), while also reflecting altruistic care and compassionate purpose (Van Dierendonck, 2011). It is a multidimensional approach. In recent years, its environmental extension has gained attention, particularly in relation to climate-focused leadership outcomes (Luu, 2020; Tuan, 2019; Afsar et al., 2018). This growing body of literature confirms a positive relationship between green leadership and environmentally responsible outcomes, highlighting its role in shaping sustainable behaviors. Sustainable consumption behavior is also influenced by individuals' financial and environmental literacy. Financial literacy enables individuals to understand the implications of consumption choices and encourages responsible spending, including the adoption of green technologies and eco-friendly products (Beny et al., 2023). Similarly, green literacy enhances environmental awareness and supports informed decision-making toward sustainable consumption. Together, these literacies form a foundational basis for promoting responsible resource use and sustainability.

Prior research identifies key determinants of sustainable consumption, including environmental concern, attitudes, social influence, and economic considerations (Durrani et al., 2023; Ur Rahman et al., 2023). Mostly individual opt the behaviors that are socially acceptable. Social influences and economic conditions are the factors that shape human social behaviors. The concept of pro-environmental identity has also emerged as a strong predictor of sustainable consumption behavior (Mayer & Carter, 2024; Wyss et al., 2022). In this context, green leadership plays a key role by influencing organizational members to adopt green policies and behaviors that support environmental performance (Kardoyo et al., 2022; Nawaz Khan, 2022). Leaders serve as role models, establish organizational priorities, and create a culture that encourages environmentally conscious practices. From a theoretical perspective, Social Learning Theory explains that employees observe and imitate the behaviors of influential leaders. When leaders consistently practice environmentally responsible behaviors, employees tend to emulate these actions. Furthermore, pro-environmental behavior contributes to organizational and individual outcomes such as efficiency, brand image, and sustainability performance, offering competitive advantages (Ku et al., 2020; Li et al., 2020). However, research on employee pro-environmental behavior remains limited, despite the evidence that leadership styles significantly influence such behaviors (Robertson & Carleton, 2018; Afsar et al., 2016). Overall, green leadership emerges as a critical driver of sustainable consumption behavior through its influence on literacy, attitudes, and pro-environmental actions of employees in banking sector.

5.1 Theoretical Implications

Our research makes a contribution to the TPB theory by (Ajzen 1991) broadening its explanatory power in the field of sustainable consumption, by demonstrating that leadership-based environmental awareness and environmental behavioral development, positively influence the connection between intention and behavior.

This study aims to extend the application of the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) by (Ajzen 1991) trying to explain how green leadership influences sustainable consumption behavior, not only cognitively, but also behaviorally. As per TPB by (Ajzen 1991), attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control are all the determinants of behavior. The results revealed that green leadership positively influences the subjective norms because it fosters an organizational culture that emphasizes environmental responsibility and sustainability. Green leaders motivate positive attitudes to pro-environment behaviors by demonstrating and supporting environmental activities (Arici & Uysal, 2022; Han et al., 2019).

In addition, the process of green literacy contributes to individual's perceived

behavioral control by building environmental knowledge and the ability to make decisions (Liu & Tobias, 2024; Law et al., 2023), so that they can make choices with greater certainty in using their sustainable consumption. Likewise, pro-environmental behavior is explained as the process of action implementation and links to the TPB, as intentions lead to behavior. The integrated model indicates that green leadership does not directly affect sustainable consumption but rather has a psychological and behavioral effect, both of which are mediated by green literacy and pro-environmental behavior.

5.2 Implications for Managers

This study's results have several management implications for companies seeking to increase environmental sustainability and encourage responsible behaviors among their employees.

Green leadership can be a strategy to create integrated training programs to boost the pro-environmental behavior of employees and make them more conscious about sustainable consumption (Li et al., 2020; Afsar et al., 2016). Another effective way managers can contribute is to encourage green literacy programs to help spread the message to workers about the environment and how it can be put to use at work. Furthermore, sustainable consumption is also an integral part of companies' business strategies; implementing this practice could help minimize the environmental footprint and enhance the sustainability performance of companies. Green leadership can also be incorporated as an essential measurement in the appraisal of executives and managers to hold them accountable for advocating environmental responsibility.

Moreover, companies can set up green teams to oversee and encourage green practices within the company's departments. To improve engagement and ownership of sustainability initiatives, employees should be actively involved in the environmental management and decision-making processes. In addition, businesses can also create awareness campaigns and incentives to promote sustainable consumption habits and environmentally friendly behavior, thereby further enhancing sustainability outcomes. As the awareness of employees regarding green issues (Sahakian & Seyfang, 2018; Lin et al., 2012) increases the knowledge of the environment can become a major part of their employees' competencies, which can be achieved through continuous training and development programs.

Once green literacy becomes part of the life of employees, environmental knowledge can be an integral competency of an employee, and this can be done through continuous training and development programs. It's also possible for organizations to partner with environmental agencies to help decrease waste and encourage sustainability on a larger scale. Besides, managers need to periodically reevaluate green leadership through effectiveness measurement to determine their sustainability goals. With time, green leadership can become a part of an organizational culture when supported by a top-down commitment, investment in green technologies, and systems that reinforce sustainable consumption in their day-to-day operations.

5.3 Limitations and Future Research

Several limitations of this study should be recognized. Firstly, the study is limited to the banking sector, which is a service-based sector. The findings are only representative of this sector and not of other sectors. Future research is indicated to broaden the model to other sectors of the service and manufacturing businesses to increase generalizations and external validity.

Secondly, the resources were invested in collecting data in a limited way. This was a student-led research project and limited resources were available to undertake the extensive data collection and field visits which may have limited the diversity of

samples.

Thirdly, the study used a purely quantitative research design with primary data from surveys. While quantitative methods offer sound statistical evidence, future studies could also include qualitative methods to deepen understanding of respondents' perceptions and contextual understanding of green leadership, green literacy, and sustainable consumption behavior. Fourth, the study failed to take into account possible method problems like the endogeneity and common method variance (CMV). Future studies are encouraged to use advanced methods such as instrumental variable methods and/or procedural or statistical remedies (such as Harman's single factor test) to enhance robustness and validity.

Furthermore, the study was somewhat biased in terms of sex of the respondents. The study did not include any control variables and did not make any distinction between men and women in terms of their inclusion in the banking sector as a whole, but this discrepancy is reflective of the overall context in which women participate in the banking sector, which in Pakistan is relatively low compared to men, due to the interplay of cultural constructs and demanding work conditions. Last, it was only banking sector that was studied. Future research is therefore recommended that would include other service sectors, e.g., insurance, telecom, and hospitality to enhance comparability and generalizability of results.

6. Conclusion

The present study explored the relationship between green leadership and sustainable consumption behavior with the mediation of green literacy and pro-environmental behavior. The results showed that green leadership has a significant effect on individual environmental awareness and the promotion of sustainable practices. In particular, green leadership contributes to the development of green literacy which gives people the knowledge and awareness to make informed decisions about the environment. It also encourages pro-environmental behavior, a direct route towards sustainable consumption.

Furthermore, both mediators had a significant effect on strengthening the effect of green leadership on sustainable consumption behavior, which shows that awareness and behavioral reinforcement are also necessary in addition to green leadership. This study identifies key steps to sustainability: leadership influence, development of literacy, engagement in behaviors and consumption decisions. The research offers strong empirical evidence for the integrated sustainability model and highlights the significance of cultivating green leadership, environmental literacy, and pro-environmental behaviors to reach long-term sustainable consumption results.

References

- Admin, A. (2023). Pakistan Banking Sector Employees Head Count Exceeded 200,000 On Record Profits. <https://augaf.com/pakistan-banking-sector-employees-head-count-exceeded-200000-on-record-profits/>
- Afsar, B., Badir, Y., and Kiani, U. S. (2016). Linking spiritual leadership and employee pro-environmental behavior: The influence of workplace spirituality, intrinsic motivation, and environmental passion. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 45, 79-88.
- Ahmad, I., and Gao, Y. (2017). Ethical Leadership and Follower's Work Attitude: The Role of Moral Identification. *Res. Humanit. Soc. Sci*, 7, 124-130.
- Akenji, L., and Bengtsson, M. (2014). Making sustainable consumption and production the core of sustainable development goals. *Sustainability*, 6(2), 513-529.

- Akhtar, S., Khan, K. U., Atlas, F., and Irfan, M. (2022). Stimulating student's pro-environmental behavior in higher education institutions: An ability–motivation–opportunity perspective. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 24(3), 4128-4149.
- Arici, H. E., and Uysal, M. (2022). Leadership, green innovation, and green creativity: A systematic review. *The Service Industries Journal*, 42(5-6), 280-320.
- Arkorful, V. E., Shuliang, Z., and Lugu, B. K. (2023). Investigating household waste separation behavior: The salience of an integrated norm activation model and the theory of planned behavior. *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management*, 66(10), 2195-2221.
- Avery, G. C. (2005). Leadership for sustainable futures: Achieving success in a competitive world. *Edward Elgar Publishing*.
- Balundė, A., Perlaviciute, G., and Truskauskaitė-Kunevičienė, I. (2020). Sustainability in youth: Environmental considerations in adolescence and their relationship to pro-environmental behavior. *Frontiers in psychology*, 11, 582920.
- Baumeister, R. F., and Vohs, K. D. (2007). Self-Regulation, ego depletion, and motivation. *Social and personality psychology compass*, 1(1), 115-128.
- Benn, S., Edwards, M., and Angus-Leppan, T. (2013). Organizational learning and the sustainability community of practice: The role of boundary objects. *Organization and Environment*, 26(2), 184-202.
- Beny, B., Wendy, W., Saleh, M., and Giriati, G. (2023). The effect of financial literacy and green innovation technology on green economic sustainability in emerging countries. *International Journal of Data and Network Science*, 7(4), 1829-1838.
- Berniak-Woźny, J., and Rataj, M. (2023). Towards green and sustainable healthcare: a literature review and research agenda for green leadership in the healthcare sector. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 20(2), 908.
- Bhawal Mukherji, S., Sekiyama, M., Mino, T., and Chaturvedi, B. (2016). Resident knowledge and willingness to engage in waste management in Delhi, India. *Sustainability*, 8(10), 1065.
- Bissing-Olson, M. J., Iyer, A., Fielding, K. S., and Zacher, H. (2013). Relationships between daily affect and pro-environmental behavior at work: The moderating role of pro-environmental attitude. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 34(2), 156-175.
- Bosnjak, M., Ajzen, I., and Schmidt, P. (2020). The theory of planned behavior: Selected recent advances and applications. *Europe's journal of psychology*, 16(3), 352.
- Brundiens, K., Barth, M., Cebrián, G., Cohen, M., Diaz, L., Doucette-Remington, S., ... and Zint, M. (2021). Key competencies in sustainability in higher education—toward an agreed-upon reference framework. *Sustainability Science*, 16, 13-29.
- Burhanudin, B., Ronny, R., and Sihotang, E. T. (2021). Consumer guilt and green banking services. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 45(1), 38-53.
- Chatterjee, S., Sreen, N., Sadarangani, P. H., and Gogoi, B. J. (2022). Impact of green consumption value, and context-specific reasons on green purchase intentions: A behavioral reasoning theory perspective. *Journal of Global Marketing*, 35(4), 285-305.
- Davis, A. E. (1996). Instrument development: getting started. *Journal of Neuroscience Nursing*, 28(3), 204-208.
- De Guimarães, J. C. F., Severo, E. A., Klein, L. L., Dorion, E. C. H., and Lazzari, F. (2023). Antecedents of sustainable consumption of remanufactured products: A

- circular economy experiment in the Brazilian context. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 385, 135571.
- Dunlap, R. E., Van Liere, K. D., Mertig, A. G., and Jones, R. E. (2000). Measuring endorsement of the new ecological paradigm: A revised NEP scale. *Journal of Social Issues*, 56(3), 425-442.
- Durrani, S., Sohail, M., and Rana, M. W. (2023). The influence of shopping motivation on sustainable consumption: A study related to eco-friendly apparel. *Journal of Social Sciences Review*, 3(2), 248-268.
- Egri, C. P., and Herman, S. (2000). Leadership in the North American environmental sector: Values, leadership styles, and contexts of environmental leaders and their organizations. *Academy of Management Journal*, 43(4), 571-604.
- Egri, C. P., and Herman, S. (2000). Leadership in the North American environmental sector: Values, leadership styles, and contexts of environmental leaders and their organizations. *Academy of Management journal*, 43(4), 571-604.
- Eva, N., Robin, M., Sendjaya, S., Van Dierendonck, D., and Liden, R. C. (2019). Servant leadership: A systematic review and call for future research. *The leadership quarterly*, 30(1), 111-132.
- Graves, L. M., Sarkis, J., and Zhu, Q. (2013). What a transformational leadership and employee motivation combine to predict employee Pro environmental behaviors in China. *Journal of environmental psychology*, 35, 81-91.
- Guba, E. G., and Lincoln, Y. S. (1994). Competing paradigms in qualitative research. *Handbook of qualitative research*, 2(163-194), 105.
- Gultom, M. (2022). Green leadership as a model of effective leadership in hospital management in the new normal era. *Bp. Int. Res. Crit. Inst.-J.(BIRCI-J.)*, 5, 1990-19910.
- Hamzah, M. I., and Tanwir, N. S. (2021). Do pro-environmental factors lead to purchase intention of hybrid vehicles? The moderating effects of environmental knowledge. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 279, 123643.
- Han, Z., Zeng, D., Li, Q., Cheng, C., Shi, G., and Mou, Z. (2019). Public willingness to pay and participate in domestic waste management in rural areas of China. *Resources, conservation and recycling*, 140, 166-174.
- Hargreaves, A. (2007). Sustainable leadership and development in education: creating the future, conserving the past. *European Journal of Education*, 42(2), 223-233.
- Haws, K. L., Winterich, K. P., and Naylor, R. W. (2014). Seeing the world through GREEN-tinted glasses: Green consumption values and responses to environmentally friendly products. *Journal of consumer psychology*, 24(3), 336-354.
- Hu, X., and Meng, H. (2023). Digital literacy and green consumption behavior: exploring dual psychological mechanisms. *Journal of Consumer Behavior*, 22(2), 272-287.
- Jain, S. (2019). Factors affecting sustainable luxury purchase behavior: A conceptual framework. *Journal of International Consumer Marketing*, 31(2), 130-146.
- Kaiser, F. G., and Fuhrer, U. (2003). Ecological behavior's dependency on different forms of knowledge. *Applied Psychology*, 52(4), 598-613.
- Kardoyo, K., Feriady, M., Farliana, N., and Nurkhin, A. (2020). Influence of the green leadership toward environmental policies support. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 7(11), 459-467.
- Karpudewan, M. (2021). The influence of ethnicity and other socio-demographic characteristics on pro-environmental attitudes: a Malaysian perspective. *Local Environment*, 26(10), 1284-1298.

- Kim, D., and Vandenberghe, C. (2020). Ethical leadership and team ethical voice and citizenship behavior in the military: The roles of team moral efficacy and ethical climate. *Group and Organization Management*, 45(4), 514-555.
- Kollmuss, A., and Agyeman, J. (2002). Mind the Gap: Why do people act environmentally and what are the barriers to pro-environmental behavior? *Environmental Education Research*, 8(3), 239-260
- Kollmuss, A., and Agyeman, J. (2002). Mind the gap: why do people act environmentally and what are the barriers to pro-environmental behavior? *Environmental education research*, 8(3), 239-260.
- Kousar, S., Afzal, M., Ahmed, F., and Bojnec, Š. (2022). Environmental awareness and air quality: The mediating role of environmental protective behaviors. *Sustainability*, 14(6), 3138.
- Koval, V. V., Havrychenko, D., Filipishyna, L., Udovychenko, I., Prystupa, L., and Mikhno, I. (2023). Behavioral economic model of environmental conservation in human resource management. *Intellectual Economics*, 17(2), 435-456.
- Kuo, L., Yeh, C. C., and Yu, H. C. (2012). Disclosure of corporate social responsibility and environmental management: Evidence from China. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 19(5), 273-287.
- Lange, F., and Dewitte, S. (2019). Measuring pro-environmental behavior: Review and recommendations. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 63, 92-100.
- Law, J. W., Lye, C. T., and Ng, T. H. (2023). Can environmental literacy and integrated behavioral factors encourage green practices at home? Evidence from Malaysia. *Cleaner and Responsible Consumption*, 10, 100134.
- Law, J. W., Lye, C. T., and Ng, T. H. (2023). Can environmental literacy and integrated behavioral factors encourage green practices at home? Evidence from Malaysia. *Cleaner and Responsible Consumption*, 10, 100134.
- Li, F., Zhang, K., Yang, P., Jiao, J., Yin, Y., Zhang, Y., and Yin, C. (2022). Information exposure incentivizes consumers to pay a premium for emerging pro-environmental food: Evidence from China. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 363, 132412.
- Li, S., Jia, R., Seufert, J. H., Tang, H., and Luo, J. (2021). As the tree is, so is the fruit? Examining the effects of ethical leadership on bootlegging from the perspective of leader–follower gender similarity. *Gender in Management: An International Journal*, 36(7), 785-800.
- Li, Y., Siddik, A. B., Masukujjaman, M., and Wei, X. (2021). Bridging green gaps: The buying intention of energy efficient home appliances and moderation of green self-identity. *Applied Sciences*, 11(21), 9878.
- Li, Z., Xue, J., Li, R., Chen, H., and Wang, T. (2020). Environmentally specific transformational leadership and employee's pro-environmental behavior: The mediating roles of environmental passion and autonomous motivation. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, 1408.
- Liden, R. C., Wayne, S. J., Liao, C., and Meuser, J. D. (2014). Servant leadership and serving culture: Influence on individual and unit performance. *Academy of management journal*, 57(5), 1434-1452.
- Lin, Y. C., Chang, C. C. A., and Lin, Y. F. (2012). Self-construal and regulatory focus influences on persuasion: The moderating role of perceived risk. *Journal of Business Research*, 65(8), 1152-1159.
- Liu, L., and Tobias, G. R. (2024). The impact of environmental literacy on residents' green consumption: Experimental evidence from China. *Cleaner and Responsible Consumption*, 12, 100165.

- Liu, L., and Tobias, G. R. (2024). The impact of environmental literacy on residents' green consumption: Experimental evidence from China. *Cleaner and Responsible Consumption*, 12, 100165.
- Luu, T. T. (2020). Integrating green strategy and green human resource practices to trigger individual and organizational green performance: The role of environmentally-specific servant leadership. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 28(8), 1193-1222.
- Maak, T., and Pless, N. M. (2006). Responsible leadership in a stakeholder society – A relational perspective. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 66(1), 99-115.
- Mayer, A., and Carter, E. (2024). Social norms, pro-environmental identity, and finances: what motivates households to participate in energy efficiency programs? *Energy Efficiency*, 17(4), 30.
- Michel, J. O. (2020). An assessment of teaching and learning about sustainability across the higher education curriculum. *Teachers College, Columbia University*.
- Mohd Suki, N., and Mohd Suki, N. (2015). Consumption values and consumer environmental concern regarding green products. *International Journal of Sustainable Development and World Ecology*, 22(3), 269-278.
- Myers, M. D. (2019). Qualitative research in business and management. *Qualitative research in business and management*, 1-364.
- Nawaz Khan, A. (2023). Is green leadership associated with employees' green behavior? Role of green human resource management. *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management*, 66(9), 1962-1982.
- Owens, L. K. (2002). Introduction to survey research design. Paper presented at the SRL fall 2002 seminar series.
- Peattie, K. (2010). Green consumption: Behavior and norms. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 35, 195-228.
- Peterson, D. (2004). Perceived leader integrity and ethical intentions of subordinates. *Leadership and Organization Development Journal*, 25(1), 7-23.
- Quoquab, F., and Mohammad, J. (2020). A review of sustainable consumption (2000 to 2020): What we know and what we need to know. *Journal of Global Marketing*, 33(5), 305-334.
- Rahaman, H. S., Stouten, J., and Guo, L. (2019). Antecedents of ethical leadership: the theory of planned behavior. *Leadership and Organization Development Journal*, 40(6), 735-746.
- Ramkissoon, H. (2020). COVID-19 Place confinement, pro-social, pro-environmental behaviors, and residents' wellbeing: A new conceptual framework. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, 2248.
- Robertson, J. L., and Barling, J. (2013). Greening organizations through leaders' influence on employees' pro-environmental behaviors. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 34(2), 176-194.
- Robertson, J. L., and Carleton, E. (2018). Uncovering how and when environmental leadership affects employees' voluntary pro-environmental behavior. *Journal of Leadership and Organizational Studies*, 25(2), 197-210.
- Robinson, K., Schmidt, T., and Teti, D. M. (2005). Issues in the use of longitudinal and cross-sectional designs. *Handbook of research methods in developmental science*, 1-20.
- Sahakian, M., and Seyfang, G. (2018). A sustainable consumption teaching review: From building competencies to transformative learning. *Journal of cleaner production*, 198, 231-241.
- Saleem, M., Qadeer, F., Mahmood, F., Ariza-Montes, A., and Han, H. (2020). Ethical

- leadership and employee green behavior: A multilevel moderated mediation analysis. *Sustainability*, 12(8), 3314.
- Savari, M., Damaneh, H. E., Damaneh, H. E., and Cotton, M. (2023). Integrating the norm activation model and theory of planned behavior to investigate farmer pro-environmental behavioral intention. *Scientific Reports*, 13(1), 5584.
- Scherbaum, C. A., Popovich, P. M., and Finlinson, S. (2008). Exploring individual-level factors related to employee energy-conservation behaviors at work 1. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 38(3), 818-835.
- Scotland, J. (2012). Exploring the philosophical underpinnings of research: Relating ontology and epistemology to the methodology and methods of the scientific, interpretive, and critical research paradigms. *English language teaching*, 5(9), 9-16.
- Sekaran, U., and Bougie, R. (2010). *Research Method for Business—A Skill Building-Approach*, John Wiley and Sons, Ltd: Singapore.
- Shalender, K., and Sharma, N. (2021). Using extended theory of planned behavior (TPB) to predict adoption intention of electric vehicles in India. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 23(1), 665-681.
- Shaw, D., Shiu, E., and Clarke, I. (2000). The contribution of ethical obligation and self-identity to the theory of planned behavior: An exploration of ethical consumers. *Journal of marketing management*, 16(8), 879-894.
- Shevchenko, T., Saidani, M., Ranjbari, M., Kronenberg, J., Danko, Y., and Laitala, K. (2023). Consumer behavior in the circular economy: Developing a product-centric framework. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 384, 135568.
- Smol, M., Avdiushchenko, A., Kulczycka, J., and Nowaczek, A. (2018). Public awareness of circular economy in southern Poland: Case of the Malopolska region. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 197, 1035-1045.
- Stern, P. C. (2000). "Toward a coherent theory of environmentally significant behavior." *Journal of Social Issues*, 56(3), 407-424.
- Sun, S., Wu, Q., and Tian, X. (2023). How does sharing economy advance cleaner production? Evidence from the product life cycle design perspective. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, 99, 107016.
- Tuan, L. T. (2020). Environmentally-specific servant leadership and green creativity among tourism employees: Dual mediation paths. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 28(1), 86-109.
- Tuan, L. T. (2021). Effects of environmentally-specific servant leadership on green performance via green climate and green crafting. *Asia Pacific Journal of Management*, 38(3), 925-953.
- Umrani, W. (2016). Moderating effect of organizational culture on the relationship between corporate entrepreneurship and business performance in Pakistan's banking sector. Universiti Utara Malaysia, Kedah Darul Aman, Malaysia.
- Ur Rahman, S., Chwialkowska, A., Hussain, N., Bhatti, W. A., and Luomala, H. (2023). Cross-cultural perspective on sustainable consumption: Implications for consumer motivations and promotion. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 25(2), 997-1016.
- Van Dierendonck, D. (2011). Servant leadership: A review and synthesis. *Journal of management*, 37(4), 1228-1261.
- Visser, W., and Courtice, P. (2011). Sustainability leadership: Linking theory and practice. *SSRN Electronic Journal*.
- Waldman, D. A., and Siegel, D. S. (2008). Defining the socially responsible leader. *Leadership Quarterly*, 19(1), 117-131.

- White, P. C., Jennings, N. V., Renwick, A. R., and Barker, N. H. (2005). Questionnaires in ecology: a review of past use and recommendations for best practice. *Journal of applied ecology*, 42(3), 421-430.
- Wyss, A. M., Knoch, D., and Berger, S. (2022). When and how pro-environmental attitudes turn into behavior: The role of costs, benefits, and self-control. *Journal of environmental psychology*, 79, 101748.
- Xin, Y., and Long, D. (2023). Linking eco-label knowledge and sustainable consumption of renewable energy: A roadmap towards green revolution. *Renewable Energy*, 207, 531-538.
- Xuerong Peng and Seoki Lee (2019) Self-discipline or self-interest? The antecedents of hotel employees' pro-environmental behaviors. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 27:9, 1457-1476
- Ying, M., Faraz, N. A., Ahmed, F., and Raza, A. (2020). How does servant leadership foster employees' voluntary green behavior? A sequential mediation model. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 17(5), 1792.
- Young, W., Hwang, K., McDonald, S., and Oates, C. J. (2010). Sustainable consumption: Green consumer behavior when purchasing products. *Sustainable Development*, 18(1), 20-31
- Zeng, Z., Zhong, W., and Naz, S. (2023). Can environmental knowledge and risk perception make a difference? The role of environmental concern and pro-environmental behavior in fostering sustainable consumption behavior. *Sustainability*, 15(6), 4791.
- Zhang, Z. X., Chen, Y. R., and Ang, S. (2014). Business leadership in the Chinese context: Trends, findings, and implications. *Management and Organization Review*, 10(2), 199-221.
- Zikmund, W. G., Babin, B. J., Carr, J. C., and Griffin, M. (2003). Business research methods 7th ed. Thomson/South-Western.